

A Study on Post Pandemic Attitude of Pre-Schoolers with Special Reference to Kolkata

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Abstract — *Pandemic caused a milestone difference in every human's life. Amongst all these, the most unnoticed area was the change in the behavioral pattern in the toddlers' pre and post pandemic. This phenomenon dragged the researcher's attention and motivated to pursue the study on this topic. Multiple preschool goers' attitude towards their attention span and classroom adjustments were collected from the preschool teachers and counselors. The study developed in several preschools of Kolkata region. The preschools were visited to collect data in the form of a questionnaire through interviews. All the collected data were analyzed qualitatively to reach the conclusion. After analyzing the data, it was clearly established that children are facing challenges to sustain their regular attention span and to adjust in the offline classes after attending online sessions, are commonly agreed by the majority of the teachers and counselors attending the preschoolers.*

Index Terms — *Behavior, Management, Pre-Schoolers, Pandemic, Attention.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The children of 2-6 years old attend the preschool for receiving the fundamental idea of formal education. Their perception of the world gets shaped largely through preschool interaction. So, any changes in the life of toddlers are observed at first hand in a preschool. The shades of changes in a child's life during post pandemic era also are primarily discovered in context with preschool scenario. The subtle yet core shift in the behavioural projection (due to pandemic) by the preschoolers gets notified through the sudden drop in their attention span and poor acceptance of real classroom after attending the online classes. These toddlers were stopped to make free moves and express themselves freely in many circumstances. Moreover,

parents offered mobile phones to manage these children locked at home 24x7. Gradually they have lost interest in real world and developed addiction to the virtual world.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The study itself arose from the positive psychology movement, which advocated the importance of identifying which strategies were employed by people who had stable mental condition this contrasted with the previous focus in psychology in a variety of settings including in the context of children and adult. As well as in schools due to the development of positive psychology programs aimed at promoting good mental health among people. Nonetheless, there have been many critiques of positive psychology, particularly in relation to its emphasis on the individual having to take responsibility of their own wellbeing, which echoes the remit of neoliberalism.

2.1. National

Trikha.A, Saini.K, (2022) stated in journal of "OORJA"-International Journal of Management and IT 20(1), under the heading of "Digitalizing child's play Post pandemic: An Exploratory study of Indian Market Place", that pandemic has opened a new market of digitalization to India, which was untouched prior pandemic. In this situation young children would grow with digital play, digital education and digital friend in form of AI, to develop a new generation called "Generation Alpha". Gupta.J, et.al. (2021) stated in journal of Tropical pediatrics 67(1), fmaa, (122), under the heading of Psychological and quarantine measures for COVID 19 pandemic on children, adolescent & caregivers: a systematic review & meta-analysis" that, various mental health issues and illness have shoot up in young children. ASD & ADHD children are more vulnerable to show worsen

symptoms. Roy.A, et.al. (2021) stated in the journal of International Journal of Social Psychiatry 67(5), 587-600, under the heading of “Mental Health implications of COVID 19 pandemic and its response in India” that, specific health issues like anxiety, depression, insomnia, denial, anger and fear have developed alarmingly post pandemic. Government has issued various consultation port through toll free no. or telepsychiatry. Mental illness is more affected in this context. Sourabh.K, Ranjan.S, (2020), stated in the journal of The Indian Journal of Paediatrics 87, 832-536, under the heading of “Compliance and psychological impact of quarantine in children and adolescent due to COVID 19 pandemic” that, comparable data was assessed for the children who could comply with emotional distress, most of the children proved non-compliant. More funds are required to raise awareness and enhance knowledge about pandemic planning. Singh.S, et.al.(2020) stated in journal of Psychiatry Research 293, 113429, under the heading of “Impact of COVID 19 and lockdown on mental health of children and adolescents: A narrative review with recommendations” that, COVID 19 has large impact on the mental health of children, there is an acute need of developmental studies for weaker children and babies from lower income group. Participation of psychologists, psychiatrists and community volunteers are recommended.

2.2. International

Marino.F, et.al. (2022) stated in journal of Clinical Medicines 11(5), 1194 under the heading of “Psychological interventions for children with autism during COVID 19 pandemic through a remote behavioral skills training program” that, Behavioral Skills Training (BST) was developed during COVID 19 to help children with ASD (Autism Spectrum Disorder). Parents got trained with BST resulting to control distress of the children due to pandemic. This also helped in reducing general symptoms in ASD children. Buchanan.D, Hargreaves.E,Quick.L, (2022) stated in journal of EDUCATION 3-13, 1-14 under the heading of “Schools closed during the Pandemic: revelations about the well being of ‘lower-attaining’ primary school children” that, the research contains experiences of 23 children regarding schooling compared with pre and post pandemic era. Pandemic affected adversely on the schooling of young children.

McCarthy.D, (2022) stated in journal JAMA pediatrics, under the heading of “Pandemic challenges may affect the toddlers in a life long way. The first three years of a human brain demands various interactions and physical activities for spontaneous growth. Pandemic paused the automatic development and left a lifelong scar in the child’s brain development. Allen.A, (2022) stated in the journal of CONVERSATION under the heading of “Pandemic babies are facing speech and social development delay” that, pandemic has increased the risk of speech delay in the young born to the double of what it was before. Less interaction and play with same aged children are the main causes of such immature development. Drouin.M, et.al. (2020) stated in the journal of cyber psychology, Behavior and Social Networking 23(11), 727-736, under the heading of “How parents and their children use social media and technology at the beginning of the COVID 19 Pandemic and associations with anxiety” that, in the early stage of COVID 19, use of social media for socializing and information gathering had increased in parent and children. This caused rise of anxiety in them, deriving a direct correlation between use of social media and higher anxiety level. They have suggested for thought design of social media campaigning.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 3.1. To know the factors that the attention spans of the pre-schoolers has dropped drastically after lockdown.
- 3.2. To recognize the challenges confronted by preschoolers to adopt offline classes after online schooling.

IV. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- 4.1 What are the factors that behind the attention spans of the pre-schoolers has dropped drastically after lockdown ?
- 4.2 What are the challenges confronted by preschoolers to adopt offline classes after online schooling ?

V. METHODOLOGY

- 5.1 Population and Sample

In this study the population is the teachers and counselors who have dealt with pre-school going children or seen them before and after the pandemic.

5.2 Study Area

This study was conducted with different pre-schools of mainly Kolkata region.

5.3 Theoretical Framework

Variables of the study contains dependent and independent variable. The study used pre-specified method for the selection of variables. The study used the health, mood and behavior of the child as dependent variable. Influence of family and school of the child was the only independent variable for the research.

5.4 Tools

For this study, the researcher have chosen “survey” as a method to collect data and then the “3 point rating scale” was used to analyse the data. Survey was conducted with a Google Form stating various statements applicable to the pre-schoolers post pandemic. In the form, each statement had three options (Agree, Neutral, and Disagree). The teacher or the counsellor under survey needs to select the option for each statement.

VI. RESULTS

- Objective 3.1: To know the factors that the attention spans of the pre-school goers has dropped drastically after lockdown.

6.1 The child quickly loses interest in any one task/ object.

Option	No. of teachers	Percentage of replies
Agree	35	70
Neutral	9	18
Disagree	6	12

(Table & Chart: 6.1)

6.2 The child doesn't complete the given task (like: eating, arranging things etc).

Option	No. of teachers	Percentage of replies
Agree	22	44
Neutral	20	40
Disagree	8	16

(Table: 6.2)

6.3 The child takes time to develop interest in any one object.

(Chart: 6.3)

6.4 The child is incompetent to complete day to day work as per his age. (Dressing up, combing, wearing shoes etc.)

(Chart: 6.4)

➤ Objective 3.2: To recognize the challenges confronted by preschoolers to adopt offline classes after online schooling.

6.5 The child avoids brain storming activity (like: puzzle, riddle, sorting games etc.)

(Chart: 6.5)

6.6 The child struggles to play in group.

(Chart: 6.6)

6.7 The child faces difficulty following simple instructions (like making a straight line, go to the corner, pick up the object etc.)

(Chart: 6.7)

6.8 The child shows less interest in physical formative activity (like: outdoor play, dance etc.)

Option	No. of teachers	Percentage of replies
Agree	19	38
Neutral	17	34
Disagree	14	28

(Table: 6.8)

6.9 The child feels shy/awkward in group activities.

(Chart: 6.9)

6.10 The child suffers to adopt different modes of teaching (like blackboard, charts, and teacher's explanation) together.

(Chart: 6.10)

DISCUSSION

From the table1 & chart 6.1 it's vivid that 70% or 35 teachers and counselors have agreed to the statement that the children lose interest quickly over a particular activity. 9 teachers of the sample i.e; 18% of the sample has given a neutral opinion. Remaining 6 teachers which cover 12% of the sample has disagreed as they have observed children maintain a longer interest span for an activity.

Here in table 6.2 it is showing that 8 teachers or 16% of the sample has not agreed the statement that the child does not complete the given task. 22 teachers

have got mixed experience so they opted neutral option. Whereas 8% disagreed as they found children can complete the task within given time.

From chart 6.3 it can be revealed that the child takes time to develop interest: for this statement 9 teachers have disagreed. 20% of the samples are neutral or not sure. 62 % of the sample i.e. 32 teachers and candidate have supported the statement, these teachers have observed children need motivation to get involved in any activity.

The chart 6.4 says that 21 samples are for the statement that the children are incompetent to complete the daily activities. 15 teachers or 30% of the samples have no clue or they are neutral about the statement. Whereas 14 participants disagreed and said that children are capable to complete their day-to-day work independently.

Chart 6.5 shows 22 teachers agreed to the statement that the child avoids brainstorming activity. 12 samples have neutral opinion, 16 teachers or 32% of the population disagreed to the statement.

The chart 6.6 displays that 23 teachers and coordinators have agreed to the statement that the children struggles to play in group, and they love to play alone. 17 teachers or 34% of the population is neutral about the statement, whereas the 10 teachers or 20% of the population does not agree to the statement.

For this statement displaying in chart 6.7, the difference in opinion is thin. As we can see, for both the options disagree and neutral 16 teachers and counselors have voted. Remaining 18 participants have voted to agree the statement.

The table 6.8 shows, there 34% of the sample or 19 teachers have no clue about the statement. They have not experienced any highlighted action of the children. 14 teachers didn't agree the statement that the child shows less interest in kinesthetic activity. Rest of the 19 counselors and teachers has supported the statement.

The feedback of this statement is surprisingly duplication of the previous statement. Here in chart 6.9 also the percentage for agreed, neutral and disagreed

participants are 38%, 34%, 28%. This means 19 participants vouch for supportive opinion for the statement, 17 participants are neutral and disagreed participant's count is 14.

Chart 6.10 showing there are 25 participants for the survey who have no specific idea about the statement as they are using single mode of teaching. 17 teachers are facing the issue that children can't adopt black board, voice explanation, and 2-d charts etc. altogether to grasp the concept. 8 participants have strongly disagreed as their experience is different; they found children have adopted multiple teaching methods comfortably.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that, it is high time to take seriously the impact of pandemic in the toddler's life. We, adult, are responsible to provide a bright and repent-less future to the next generation. All the stakeholders like: parents, society, pre-schools, need to take active steps that take the generation to a prosperous journey. Children are like clay dough; they will follow their parents and teacher in their life. So, the adults need to model correct behaviour and portray more care and gentleness towards the toddlers. Meanwhile, value education and creative influence will convert them into a happier human being, so these elements also need to be considered.

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